

2015

APR-MAY

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

***(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 0.948***

V O L - I V I s s u e s : I I I

***Chief-Editor:
Ubale Amol Baban***

**TECHNOPHOBIA OF TEACHERS TOWARDS WEB BASED TEACHING AND
EXPERIENCE LEARNING**

KULDEEP

Research Scholar

Dept. of Education

Kuruksetra University

kurukshetra

SANDEEP KAUR

Yash College of Education

Rurkee, Rohtak

Abstract

In the 21st century, competencies in education are seen more in line with Web based teaching. And it is evident that web based teaching have the potential to enhance access, quality and effectiveness in education and to enable the development of more and better teachers in India. Only a creative and enthusiastic teacher can incorporate the modern development of Web based teaching in the classroom very successfully. When teacher lack the necessary confidence to integrate a technology into their lessons, they tend to ignore it. Access to resources, quality of software and hardware ease of use incentives to change support collegiality in the school and commitment to professional learning are among other factors influencing teacher's decision to use new technologies in the classroom. Many factors contribute to the attitude and skill of using technology in the classroom by teachers in education. One important factor is technophobia where teachers show fear of or revulsion to modern technology. The main cause of technophobia is ignorance. The people who shun technology are generally the people who don't understand it.

Key Word:- *Technophobia, Teachers, Web Based Teaching And Experience Learning.*

Introduction

In today's global and competitive environment which is marked by the coming of Information society, using the technologies o web learning becomes a widely accepted way of training and standardization of the overall education process they offer. The information society requires the use of technology enhanced learning and teaching at different education forms and level. The basis of web based teaching is combination, implementation and relationship of the activities for learning and teaching via different electronic media.

Education is the only means to incorporate web based teaching in the development aspects of the society. Web Based teaching in education refers to the use of educational technologies in teaching and learning process. Web Based teaching is used as a tool to enable the teachers for teaching and subjects ranging from arts to sciences. There is evidence to show that learning when computer aided instruction or computer aided learning is used compared to the conventional method (Biswas 1994).

Web based teaching has not only changed the role of teachers in classrooms but also provided them with a large number of software and websites which can be utilized for educational purposes Power Point, Ms-Word and Excel are among the most commonly used software packages in schools today and their pedagogical benefits and contributions to learning and teaching have been studied and tested long ago. Traditional forms of teacher education are transformed, as the Internet becomes a new medium for communication. Traditionally teachers have fulfilled dual roles as presenters of structured information and social agents in the educational process. Students are in need of good interactive resources with learning tools and techniques.

Teacher education institution and programs need to model the new pedagogies and tools for learning with the aim of enhancing the teaching – learning process. Moreover, they must also give guidance in determining how the new technologies can be best used in the context of culture, needs and economic conditions of their country. Web based teaching has great potential for enhancing teaching and learning outcomes.

The realization of this potential depends much on how the teacher uses the technology. This would in turn depend, among other things, on the kind of training that the teacher has undergone. Many factors contribute to the attitude and skill of using technology in the classroom by teachers in education. One important factor is ‘technophobia’ where teachers show fear of or revulsion to modern technology. The main cause of technophobia is ignorance. The people who shun technology are generally the people who don’t understand it.

Many technophobes are worried about technology taking over. They are worried that humans will become as obsolete as technology itself can become, and that the more reliant humans are on technology, the more humanity is lost.

The most common reactions technophobes when using a computer is self-doubt. They are constantly afraid that if they hit the wrong button, something terrible will happen, like the computer blowing up or some other rather ridiculous event. The people who shun technology are generally the people who don’t understand it. The main cause of technophobia is ignorance. Most people who hate technology hate it for the simple fact that it isn’t what they are used to. Usually, technophobia inflicts the older generation, the generation who hasn’t grown up with

computer games etc. Another thing that they don't like is that the fact that they are being taught by those younger than them, either a young adult, which is the exact opposite of how the usual passing of knowledge system works.

Review of Literature

Azarfam & Jabbari (2012) It is observed that the use of technology is determined by a wide range of factors, ranging from external factors such as access to appropriate materials and professional development opportunities to more internal factors such as awareness of the benefits of technology and personal attitudes towards technological innovations, and the persistence of traditional education in some educational settings due to the absence of professional training leads the researcher to the conclusion that it is necessary to train teachers about new technologies, so that the contents to be produced can be used letting instructors to relieve from computer anxiety.

Hong (2009) This article would also help technophobic teachers who were used to analyzing the results manually by counting the students' responses from the traditional paper-based questionnaires/surveys to instantly and conveniently use online surveys to get qualitative and quantitative data from their students' responses with just a few clicks. In this article, the researcher will share the following aspects: 1) the need to use online surveys at secondary and postsecondary level; 2) the definition of technophobia and the need to train technophobic teachers to use technology; 3) the definition of an online survey; 4) and a sharing of how to create an online survey that can be easily made by one of the online survey providers on the Web.

Lam(2006) Technophilia vs. Technophobia: A Preliminary look at why second-language teachers do or do not use technology in their classrooms. Given the increasing pressure exerted by technological developments on education, it is important to understand the perceived 'technophobia' of teachers and to determine whether fear is the underlying factor behind their decisions regarding technology. Oral interviews were conducted with 10 L2 teachers and analyzed for their content in light of the following questions: (1) What are the reasons behind L2 teachers' decisions to use technology for teaching? (2) Why do some L2 teachers choose not to use computers in their teaching? (3) What factors influence these decisions? The main reasons are related to the teacher's personal belief in technology's benefits, or lack thereof, rather than to a resistance to technology. This finding suggests that teachers are not really 'technophobic' and that institutions are perhaps overly 'technophilic' in their rush to obtain the latest innovations without considering the needs of teachers and students.

Regina et al (2004) examined the incidence of technophobia and the attitudes of teachers towards online learning and teaching technologies. The study revealed that public school

teachers are generally more afraid of computers than their peers working in private schools. Older teachers are more afraid of technology than younger ones.

H. Kato (2004) revealed in his study the need for sharing of education knowledge as well as some potential problems such as unfamiliarity with personal computers, negative attitude with personal computers, negative attitude towards making lesson plans, anxiety regarding privacy protection, resistance to mutual evaluation, evaluation of knowledge and undeveloped give and take relationship.

Significance of the study

Technology integration is a complex phenomenon that involves understanding teacher's motivations, perceptions and beliefs about learning of technology (Keengwe and Onchwari, 2008).

Many factors contribute to the attitude and skill of using technology in the classroom by teachers in education. One such factor is "technophobia" where teachers show fear of or revulsion to modern technology. Sometimes the term "technophobia" is used in the sense of an irrational fear while other defend that the fears are justified. The main cause of technophobia is ignorance on teacher's part and the article review shows that very less work has been done on technophobia of teachers so the researcher decided to work in this area or domain.

Statement of the problem

Technophobia Of Teachers Towards Web Based Teaching And Experience Learning.

Operational definitions

Technophobia

Technophobia means a negative psychological reaction to technology, either mild or severe. Technophobia is the fear or dislike of advanced technology or complex devices, especially computers. The term is generally used in the sense of an irrational fear. It is opposite of technophiles. "Technophobia" and "computer phobia" are terms which can be used interchangeably.

Technophobia in teachers

Technophobia in teachers can be due to uncomfortable with many forms of technology like computers, internet, podcasting etc. The teachers who shun technology are generally the teachers who don't understand it. Most teachers who hate technology hate it for the simple fact that it isn't what they are used to.

Web based teaching

Web based teaching are a subset of computer based training or electronic learning used to leverage the World Wide Web for the delivery of instructional materials. Web based teaching emerged as elements on personal websites with the proliferation and adoption of the internet.

Experience Learning

Experience learning is the process of making meaning from direct experience. It is the process of internally examining and exploring an issue of concern, triggered by an experience, which creates and clarifies meaning in terms of self, and which results in a changed conceptual perspective. Experience learning focuses on the learning process for the individual.

Objectives

- To study the technophobia of teachers handling high school and higher secondary classes towards web based teaching and experience learning.
- To study the difference in the technophobia of teachers who have used web based teaching in the classrooms and in those who have not used web based even once in their teaching.

Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference in the technophobia of teachers handling high school and higher secondary classes towards web based teaching and experience learning.
- There is significant difference in the technophobia of teachers who have used web based teaching regularly in the classroom and in those who have not used web based even once in their teaching.

Design of the Study

Sample

About 100 teachers of private school of Delhi teaching secondary and higher secondary classes, constituted the sample for the present study. Equal weightage was given to the aided and unaided schools of Delhi.

Methodology

In order to realize the above said objectives, **Descriptive Survey Method** was employed.

Tool to be used

In the present study a Computer Attitude Scale (CAS) by **Dr. Tahira Khatoon (Aligarh)** and **Manika Sharma (Aligarh)** has been used by the investigator. The CAS consists of five areas as computer anxiety, computer confidence, computer interest, computer as a useful tool and computer career. It includes 20 items in which 11 are positive items and 9 are negative items. Each area contains four items in a five-point likert response format. On the basis of Computer Aided Scale, the total students can be divided into 3 groups.

Attitude Level (Category)	Scores
Positive Computer Attitude	64-100
Neutral Computer Attitude	57-63
Negative Computer Attitude	20-56

Interpretation and Analysis

- 1) Comparison of Technophobic and Non-Technophobic attitude of Male and Female teachers towards Web Based Teaching and Experience Learning

Variables /Categories	Non-Technophobia		Technophobia	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Mean	80.88	74.87	49.00	37.91
Standard Deviation	6.88	5.25	2.449	5.26

t-ratio	7.76	10.66	
Level of significance	significant	significant	

From the table 1- it is evident that female teachers are more technophobic ($X=49$) in comparison to which indicates male teachers ($X=37.916$) towards web based teaching which indicates that sex plays a significant role in determining the technophobia of male and female teachers towards web based teaching. The t-ratio of technophobic teachers of both categories male and female is 10.665 and t-ratio of non-technophobic teachers of both categories male and female is 7.768, both values are significant.

2) Comparison of technophobic and non technophobic attitude of Experienced technology users teachers and In-Experienced technology users teachers towards Web Based Teaching and Experience Learning.

3)

Variables /Categories	Non-Technophobia		Technophobia	
	Experienced Technology users	In-Experienced Technology Users	Experienced Technology Users	In-Experience Technology Users
Mean	82.44	74.87	49.60	41.50
Standard Deviation	7.53	6.20	6.18	5.80
t-ratio	13.33		5.11	
Level of significance	significant		significant	

From the table 2- That the technophobia among the teachers is affected by less or more knowledge and experience of using web based teaching in the classrooms and with those who are frequent users of web based in the classroom in comparison to those who have not used web based even once in their learning. In-experienced technology users are more technophobic ($X=41.5$) in comparison to experienced technology users ($X=49.6$). The t-ratio of technophobic and non-technophobic teachers are significant.

Conclusion

- Teachers of senior secondary classes are more technophobic in comparison to teachers of secondary classes towards web based teaching and experience learning.
- Experienced technology users teachers have less technophobia in comparison to non-experienced technology users towards web based teaching and experience learning.

Educational Implication

Technology is here to stay. That's the simple truth. How we prepare for a world that is so dramatically different from what is a decade or so ago is to prepare ourselves for the next decade.

- Hold seminars, workshops and brown bag lunches on technophobia. The more we share information and knowledge on the topic, the easier it becomes for individuals to recognize that they have a problem.
- Teachers should not only be trained in the use of hardware and software, but also on how to use web based in teaching-learning process.
- There should be some reward for the use of technology and teachers should be helped to realize that effectiveness in teaching and research can be enhanced by using technology. Thus principal has to devise specific and varied strategies to motivate teachers to use web based technology.

References:-

- Bahrani Taher (2012). Technology and Language Learning: Language Learners' Attitude. *Advances in Asian Social Science* 1(1), 20-23. World Science Publisher.
- Khatoun, T. & Sharma, M. (2000). *Computer Attitude Scale*. H.P. Bhargava Book House.
- Aggarwal, Y.P. (2000). *Statistical methods : Concepts, application and computation*. New Delhi: Sterling Publisher Pvt. Ltd.

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(Bi-Monthly) Peer-Reviewed Journal Vol No IV Issues III
APRIL-MAY 2015 ISSN 2278-5655

Aggarwal, Y.P. (2008). *The science of educational research* : Kuruksheetra : Nirmal Book Agency.

Garrett, H.E. (2007). *Statistics in psychology and education*. Bombay: Vakils, Feffer

Good, C.V. (1959) *Dictionary of education* (2nd ed.). New York: McGraw Hill Book Company Inc.

Maddux, C. D., & Johnson, D. L. (2009). Information technology in education: The need for a critical examination of popular assumptions. *Computers in the Schools*, 26(1), 1-3.

Hong, LIP Paul Chi (2009). Evaluating Teaching and Learning from Students' Perspectives in Their Classroom through Easy-to-Use Online Surveys. *International Journal of Cyber Society and Education* Pages 33-48, Vol. 1, No. 1, March 2008

Poirier, TI. & O'Neil, C.K. (2000). Use of web technology and active learning strategies in a quality assessment methods course. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 64. Retrieved May 31, 2007, from <http://www.ajpe.org/legacy/pdfs/aj640311.pdf>

Lam, Y. (2006). Technophilia vs. Technophobia: A Preliminary look at why second-language teachers do or do not use technology in their classrooms. *Canadian Modern language review/ La Revue Canadienne des Langues vivantes*, pages 389-420, Vol. 56(3).

Copyrights @ Kuldeep & Sandeep Kaur..This is an open access peer reviewed article distributed under the creative common attribution license which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provide the original work is cited.